

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Thermal Decomposition and Acid Association of Salts $[\text{ReO}_4\text{py}_4]^+$

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The preparation and the properties of pentavalent rhenium compounds containing the cation $[\text{ReO}_4\text{py}_4]^+$ have been described in previous communications¹. The composition of the air-dried salts, their thermal decomposition and acid association of $[\text{ReO}_4\text{py}_4]^+$ are described in the present paper.

The analysis of dioxotetrapyridinerhenium (V) chloride prepared by our method¹ and dried in air corresponded to the dihydrate, $[\text{ReO}_4\text{py}_4] \text{Cl} \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, but when dried in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide it became anhydrous. The composition of the corresponding cyanide was essentially the same, while the perchlorate was anhydrous when dried in air.

The acid association constants of $[\text{ReO}_4\text{py}_4]^+$ have been determined by Bjerrum's method by titrating an aqueous solution of $[\text{ReO}_4\text{py}_4] \text{Cl}$ with standard hydrochloric acid at 27°, the ionic strength being maintained 0.5 with potassium chloride. For the first protonation

$\log k_1$ was found to be 1.6. The second proton association to form $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2\text{py}_4]^{3+}$ is extremely weak and k_2 could not be measured.

A solution of $[\text{ReO}_4\text{py}_4] \text{Cl}$ in 0.4 N HCl when allowed to stand gave a dirty green precipitate. The precipitate was washed with 0.4 N HCl and then with ethanol. The residue on extraction with acetone gave a pink solution leaving behind a green residue. The pink solution was evaporated in air to give a violet substance which was then dried over H_2SO_4 . The analysis of both the violet and green substances corresponded to $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_4 \text{Cl}$. The violet substance on standing slowly turned dirty green and finally pure green without any change in composition. Both were diamagnetic, but after making diamagnetic corrections for the ligands a small paramagnetism ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0.69 \text{ B.M.}$ at 306° K) remained for Re (V) in the green complex, while the violet complex was still diamagnetic ($\chi'_M = -50 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs units). The I.R. spectra in nujol mull of the violet and the green forms gave $\text{Re}=\text{O}$ stretch at 977 (w) and 980 (m) cm^{-1} respectively. In addition the violet form gave characteristic OH frequencies at 3330 (s) cm^{-1} , while the green form gave no bands in the region 300–5000 cm^{-1} . It thus appears that in the green complex no free

OH group is present. It may be a highly polymerised compound. The violet complex probably undergoes polymerisation to the green one through the release of water by the condensation of OH groups of a number of its molecules. The actual extent of polymerisation could not be determined. The green complex is probably identical with that reported by Beard *et al.*²

Boiling of either of the violet or the green complex or of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ with 6N or concentrated hydrochloric acid gave the previously reported¹ green compound $[\text{ReOpy}_2\text{Cl}_2]$. Its saturated aqueous solution ($2.01 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$) was practically nonconducting ($\mu_{\nu} = 18.7 \text{ ohm}^{-1}$ at 30°) and the compound did not precipitate silver chloride on tritaring in cold with silver nitrate solution. This was also diamagnetic, but the corrected moment was 0.43 B.M. at 303°K . Its I.R. spectra gave very strong $\text{Re}=\text{O}$ stretching frequency at 970 cm^{-1} , but OH frequency was absent.

The thermogravimetric and the differential thermal analysis curves of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4](\text{CN}) \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been recorded. The first weight loss in the T.G.A. curve of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ occurred at about 100° and continued upto 160° and the weight loss in this region corresponds to the loss of two molecules of water. Thereafter the loss was quite steep and continued upto 210° after which a fairly constant weight horizontal extended upto 250° . The total loss in weight at this stage was 38.0%. On heating a sample of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at a constant temperature of 160° , almost constant weight stage was obtained when the loss was about 37.0% and the residue left was dark green in colour from which an acetone-soluble pink substance of the composition $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{py}_2$ and an insoluble green substance $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_3\text{py}_4\text{Cl}_4$ were obtained. The thermal decomposition of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ can thus be represented as

The calculated weight loss on this basis is 38.0%.

$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{py}_2$ is a heavy pink substance, insoluble in water and ethanol, but dissolves in alkali solution to give initially a brown solution which very easily turns colourless with the liberation of pyridine and formation of perchlorate. $\text{Re}_2\text{O}_3\text{py}_4\text{Cl}_4$ is probably the same green substance as previously reported by Johnson, Taha and Wilkinson³.

The D.T.A. curve of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl} \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ showed a very pronounced endothermic peak at 185° followed by a weak exothermic one at 260° . The endothermic peak probably represents the volatilisation of water and pyridine and the weak exothermic peak at 260° is probably due to the partial oxidation of Re (V) to Re (VII).

The T.G.A. and the D.T.A. curves of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4](\text{CN}) \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ were essentially of the same nature as the chloride.

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